

On the drivers of ice nucleating particle variability for Eastern Mediterranean orographic clouds

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Abstract

We report the drivers of spatiotemporal variability of ice nucleating particles (INPs) for mixed-phase orographic clouds (~ -25°C) in the Eastern Mediterranean. In the planetary boundary layer, pronounced INP diurnal periodicity is observed, which is mainly driven by biological and dust particles but not biomass burning aerosol particles. The comparison of size-resolved and fluorescence-discriminated aerosol particle properties with INPs reveal the primary role of fluorescent biological aerosol particles. The presence of Saharan dust increases INPs during nighttime more than daytime, because of stronger dust layer intrusions and less availability of boundary layer aerosols with lower boundary layer height. However, INP diurnal periodicity is absent in the free troposphere, despite any observed dependence of INPs on bioaerosol and dust particle abundance. Given the effective ice nucleation ability of bioaerosols at warm temperatures and subsequent effects from ice multiplication, the lack of such cycles in models point to important, overlooked cloud formation cycles in mountainous regions.

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30 INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric ice nucleation plays a vital role in cloud formation and cloud microphysical properties, which considerably influences regional and global precipitation, hydrological cycle¹, atmospheric radiative forcing² and the Earth's energy balance³⁻⁴. For temperature (T) lower than -38°C , atmospheric ice formation can occur spontaneously via homogeneous freezing⁵. However, for warmer temperatures, the initiation of cloud ice formation in most clouds necessitates ice nucleating particles (INPs) that heterogeneously freeze⁶. **Considering the strong impacts INPs can have on cloud properties, through a minor fraction of total particles⁷**, INPs can bear a large impact on the hydrological cycle and the climate⁸.

The ice formation ability and the abundance of INPs depend on temperature, particle types and their degree of atmospheric aging⁹. It is well known that dust particles from desert and agricultural lands⁷, biological particles and soil dust may contain biological material⁹ and constitute major sources of INPs for warmer mixed-phase clouds (MPCs), together with regionally black carbon and organic particles from biomass burning emissions for colder cirrus clouds^{4,6}. Moreover, air mass transport¹⁰⁻¹¹ and atmospheric aging processes¹²⁻¹³ can modulate INP concentrations and characteristics¹⁴. The large uncertainty of the spatiotemporal variability of INPs^{7,15} (both abundance and distribution), together with the uncertainty of subsequent cloud processes such as ice multiplication¹⁶⁻¹⁸, leads to large uncertainty in the effects of INPs in regional and global weather, climate, and Earth system models^{4,9}. Therefore, there is a significant need to improve the predictability of INPs in models⁸.

Driven by periodic (seasonal and diurnal) solar radiation and anthropogenic activities and their effects on aerosol sources¹⁹, INPs may also exhibit a following periodicity²⁰⁻²¹. **Previous studies reported** a seasonal periodicity of INPs in different regions²²⁻²⁴, however, studies about INP variabilities within a day are still scarce, owing to the insufficient time resolution of offline INP spectrometers, short duration of observations and incomplete attribution of INP sources. Diurnal variability of INPs can be an especially important driver for ice formation in orographic cloud systems, given their especially dynamic nature that requires high time resolution of INPs for accurate predictions. Rosinski et al.²⁵ found that INPs (at -15 and -20°C) show concentration maxima at 06:00 and 18:00 local time of the day. Despite the short duration and time resolution of the data (4 hours), the results from Rosinski et al.²⁵ suggested an INP diurnal cycle that subsequent studies supported^{11,23,25-26}, albeit with limited insights on the implications. For example, Isono et al.²⁶ reported no appreciable diurnal variations for INPs (at -15°C) observed at the Manuna Loa observatory at ~ 3400 m above sea level (a.s.l.) (Hawaii, US) using an offline static cloud chamber to measure INPs every ~ 6 hours. Wieder et al.¹¹ observed INPs at the Weissfluhjoch mountaintop (2693 m a.s.l., Alps) at Davos, Switzerland every 2 hours using an offline droplet freezing assay and found a diurnal cycle of INPs showing a minimum in the morning and a peak after sunset. Night time observations, however, were missing¹¹. Recently, the availability of automated online INP spectrometers²⁷⁻²⁸ with high temporal resolution ability facilitates investigations on the INP diurnal periodicity. Using an automated continuous flow diffusion chamber, Brunner et al.²³ performed a year-long continuous INP observations at a high altitude observatory at Jungfraujoch (~ 3580 m a.s.l., Alps, Switzerland) and reported the diurnal periodicity of INPs for days only with planetary boundary layer (PBL) air mass intrusions without Saharan dust events. However, specific aerosol source that drives the diurnal cycles was not determined²³. Temporal changes of INPs also

depend on the air mass origin at the site, given that the diurnal cycle of aerosols shows differences if it originates from the PBL or free troposphere (FT)²⁹⁻³⁰. Contrast to these studies, Wieder et al.¹¹ found no diurnal cycles of INPs at Wolfgangpass (1632 m a.s.l., Alps, at Davos) which tends to reside in the PBL during the observation period, but different from another in parallel observation site near Weissfluhjoch (~1.0 km higher) at the mountaintop. Therefore, determining the atmospheric condition of the observation site is necessary for investigating the INP abundance and its diurnal periodicity.

In mountainous regions, local or regional biological particle emission²⁰ sources in the PBL exhibiting a diurnal cycle may regulate INP variabilities; thus the diurnal changes of PBLH may also regulate the availability of aerosol particles from sources in the PBL³¹. Of particular interest is the importance of bioaerosols, since most often forested areas are in mountainous regions. If not forested, arid regions could also be sources of dust, given that mountain flows in general can generate high velocities that are capable of lifting large amounts of dust. Such processes are poorly described or lacking in models, thus it is critical to assess their importance for INP diurnal variability. This is because when combined with the effects of ice multiplication they can generate heavy snowfall and extreme precipitation close to the ground during winter storms, which is demonstrated in a modelling study¹⁸ in parallel with this study during the same field campaign.

In this study, we present the diurnal variability of INPs and the drivers thereof for orographic MPCs in the Eastern Mediterranean. The data were collected during a field campaign, the Cloud-Aerosol InteractionS in the Helmos background Troposphere (CALISHTO, <https://calishto.panacea-ri.gr/>) between October and November, 2021. CALISHTO was conducted at the Helmos Hellenic Atmospheric Aerosol and Climate Change (in short as (HAC)² hereafter) station (37.9843° N, 22.1963° E, 2314 m a.s.l.) close to the summit of Mt. Helmos in the Peloponnese. The diurnal cycle of INPs was determined for a variety of atmospheric states, including the relative position of the (HAC)² with respect to the PBL, air mass origin and the effect of Saharan dust events. The PBL property and detailed INP source apportionment results achieved in parallel works for CALISHTO³²⁻³³ aid the determination of the drivers for INP cycles. We examine the distinct contributions of bioaerosol and dust to the diurnal cycle and express the INP distribution in relation to the PBL height (PBLH).

85 RESULTS

Determination of atmospheric conditions at (HAC)²

(HAC)² contributes data to the Global Atmospheric Watch and ACTRIS programs since 2016 and is located near the summit of Mt. Helmos at the heart of the Peloponnese in Greece. (HAC)² is frequently situated in the FT or at the FT/PBL interface³¹ at a cross-road of different air masses, each of which is characterized as different INP sources³². The observational setup of CALISHTO is presented in the Supplementary Fig. S1, and also elsewhere in detail³², including high resolution measurements of in-situ INPs (~6–7 min), microphysical and chemical aerosol properties at (HAC)², remote sensing measurements conducted at Vathia Lakka (VL) lower than (HAC)² by ~0.5 km and back trajectory analysis for calculating the origin of air masses sampled at (HAC)². Timeseries of measurement results are presented and introduced in Fig. S2 and Text S2 in the Supplementary. The PBLH measured by the wind lidar at VL, i.e. the distance between VL and the FT/PBL interface, is used

95 to determine whether $(\text{HAC})^2$ is in the PBL^{31} by comparing PBLH with the distance between $(\text{HAC})^2$ and VL, i.e. ~ 0.5 km (illustrated in Supplementary Fig. S1). We also compare the concentration of particles between 95 nm and 800 nm ($\text{SMPS}_{>95\text{nm}, <800\text{nm}}$) measured by a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS, model 3938, TSI Inc., US) with a threshold value (100 std cm^{-3}) to determine if the site is in the $\text{PBL}^{32,34}$ when PBLH from lidar remote sensing measurements is not available. A thorough evaluation against other metrics and the $\text{PBLH}^{31,35}$ demonstrated that the site is in the PBL when $\text{SMPS}_{>95\text{nm}, <800\text{nm}}$ exceeds

100 std cm^{-3} , given a general fact that aerosols in the FT will be diluted after transporting from far-away PBL sources³¹. Throughout the whole campaign, our results show that $\text{SMPS}_{>95\text{nm}, <800\text{nm}}$ is generally (for 82.5% of the period) larger than 100 std cm^{-3} when $(\text{HAC})^2$ is in the PBL ($\text{PBLH} > 0.5 \text{ km}$), while $\text{SMPS}_{>95\text{nm}, <800\text{nm}}$ is generally (for 85.0% of the period) smaller than 100 std cm^{-3} when $(\text{HAC})^2$ is outside of the PBL ($\text{PBLH} < 0.5 \text{ km}$).

105 **Fig. 1** Diurnal cycles of PBLH measured by wind lidar³¹ at the VL site (on the left axis) and corresponding diurnal cycles of the number concentration of particles with diameter between 95 nm and 800 nm ($\text{SMPS}_{>95\text{nm}, <800\text{nm}}$) measured at $(\text{HAC})^2$ (on the right axis). Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th quartiles. The horizontal dashed red line indicates both the altitude difference between $(\text{HAC})^2$ and the lidar (~ 0.5 km) and the threshold particle number value of 100 std cm^{-3} ^{31,35}. Different $(\text{HAC})^2$ atmospheric conditions are classified in different panels. (a)

110 All observations during the campaign. (b) $(\text{HAC})^2$ in the FT throughout the day. (c) $(\text{HAC})^2$ in the PBL throughout the day. (d) $(\text{HAC})^2$ in the PBL throughout the day without dust event influence. (e) $(\text{HAC})^2$ in the PBL throughout the day with dust event

influence. (f) (HAC)² for days with both PBL and FT influences. The data points of each (HAC)² position scenario are resampled for every 20 min and each panel shows a period cycle of 24 h starting at 00:00 UTC+2 (local time) of the day.

Depending on the (HAC)² position with respect to the FT/PBL interface (indicated by PBLH), we classify its atmospheric scenario. The scenarios include (HAC)² in FT throughout the day (Fig. 1b for PBLH<0.5 km, 5 days), (HAC)² in PBL throughout the day (Fig. 1c for PBLH>0.5 km, 9 days), and (HAC)² partially in the PBL throughout the day (Fig. 1f, 30 days), which is termed (HAC)²~PBL means (HAC)² fluctuates around PBL/FT interface. Continuous dust events were recorded between November 5 and 9 (Supplementary Fig. S2). Thus, we further divide the scenario of (HAC)² in the PBL throughout the day into two cases, i.e. without (Fig. 1d, 4 days) and with (Fig. 1e, 5 days) dust events – to investigate the effect of Saharan dust events on INP variability. The presence of dust event is determined by significant increase in coarse-sized particles (>2.5 μm), low Ångström exponent (<1)³² from optical scattering measurement and the spatiotemporal dust distribution predicted by modelling experiments (Supplementary Fig. S2c, d and f respectively). For the scenario of (HAC)² in FT throughout the day (Fig. 1b), no appreciable diurnal cycle is seen for both PBLH and SMPS_{>95nm, <800nm}, while a clear diurnal cycle is observed for days where the (HAC)² is in the PBL (Fig. 1c), showing the maximum in the afternoon. The drivers of PBLH diurnal cycles are discussed in Supplementary Text S3 based on results in Figs. S3 to S6. We note that larger SMPS_{>95nm, <800nm} concentrations of non-dust days (Fig. 1d) compared with those of dust days (Fig. 1e) are because of difference in aerosol sources. On non-dust days, PBL is influenced by continental aerosols enriched in fine mode particles (generally <500 nm), whereas the presence of dust events on dust days tends to shift the size distribution of aerosols to larger particle with a depletion in fine mode particles according to parallel studies on the aerosol sources³² and PBLH³⁶ at (HAC)² during CALISHTO campaign. This is also supported by results presented in Supplementary S4 showing the diurnal cycles of aerosol particles in different size ranges (in particular for particles <500 nm, see Figs. S7 and S8).

INP diurnal cycles under different atmospheric conditions

135 **Fig. 2** Diurnal cycles of INP (tested at $T=-25.2\pm 1.4^\circ\text{C}$, on the left axis) and $\text{APS}_{>0.5\mu\text{m, total}}$ (the total number concentration of particles between 0.5 and 20 μm measured by an Aerodynamic Particle Sizer, on the right axis) measured at $(\text{HAC})^2$ under different atmospheric conditions. Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th quartiles. Different $(\text{HAC})^2$ atmospheric conditions are classified in different panels. (a) All observations during the campaign. (b) For days only in the FT. (c) For days only in the PBL. (d) Days in the PBL without dust events. (e) Days in the PBL with dust events. (f) Observations for days not exclusively in the PBL or FT. The data points of each scenario are resampled for every 20 min and each panel shows a cycle period of 24 h starting at 00:00 UTC+2 (local time) of the day. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ), as well as corresponding p values, are provided to evaluate the correlation between INP concentration and $\text{APS}_{>0.5\mu\text{m, total}}$. The P value is the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value if there is no linear correlation between INP and $\text{APS}_{>0.5\mu\text{m, total}}$. The number of data points (n) for each case of above statistical analysis is 72.

145 Analysis of the INPs over 24h periods (e.g. Fig. 2) reveals that INPs at $(\text{HAC})^2$ follow diurnal periodicities depending on the PBL condition. The INP number concentration was tested by a portable ice nucleation experiment (PINE) at $T=-25.2\pm 1.4^\circ\text{C}$ in the mixed phase cloud regime (Fig. S2b). PINE samples aerosols from an omnidirectional total inlet and tests INPs in all freezing mode by addressing supersaturated conditions with respect to water³². Median INP concentration overall increases from 3.0 std L^{-1} during daybreak to a maximum of 12.0 std L^{-1} in the early afternoon (12:00–15:00) and subsequently decreases to approximately 3.0 std L^{-1} (Fig. 2a). Then it remains a fairly constant level of 2.0–3.0 std L^{-1} throughout the evening until 150 the early morning (at 3:00), after which the concentration occasionally spikes up to $\sim 10.0 \text{ std L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2a). Fig. 2 shows that

the INP diurnal patterns for days when (HAC)² is influenced by PBL airmasses (Fig. 2c, d, e and f) are generally analogous to the overall INP diurnal periodicity presented in Fig. 2a but show different maximum and minimum values, however, INPs for days only in the FT (Fig. 2b) do not exhibit such a diurnal cycle but generally show median concentration values less than 3.0
 155 std L⁻¹ throughout the day. The above results suggest that the source of INPs observed at (HAC)² originates primarily from the PBL, and that the diurnal cycle of INPs is driven by the influx of aerosol particles from the PBL to the site. This is consistent with Brunner et al.²³, that found for Jungfraujoch, an absence of a diurnal cycle was observed when the site is in the FT but a clear diurnal cycle is observed when influenced by PBL airmasses.

160 **Fig. 3** Diurnal cycles of INP (tested at $T=-25.2\pm 1.4^{\circ}\text{C}$, on the left axis) and the concentration of aerosol particles between 2.5 and 20
 165 μm ($\text{APS}_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$, on the right axis) measured at (HAC)² under different atmospheric conditions. Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th quartiles. Different (HAC)² atmospheric conditions are classified in different panels. (a) All observations during the campaign. (b) For days only in the FT. (c) For days only in the PBL. (d) Days in the PBL without dust events. (e) Days in the PBL with dust events. (f) Observations for days not exclusively in the PBL or FT. The data points of each scenario are resampled for every 20 min and each panel shows a cycle period of 24 h starting at 00:00 UTC+2 (local time) of the day. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ), as well as corresponding p values, are provided to evaluate the correlation between INP concentration and $\text{APS}_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$. The p value is the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value if there is no linear correlation between INPs and $\text{APS}_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$. The number of data points (n) for each case of above statistical analysis is 72.

Table 1. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ) for the relationship evaluation between diurnal INP median number concentration and the median number concentration of aerosol particles with different sizes under different atmospheric conditions. A critical p value of 0.05 from F-test for R and ρ is used to assess the significance level of the relationship. A p value smaller than 0.05 suggests that the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value is less than 5% if there is actually no linear correlation between INPs and the given parameter, thus the calculated R (ρ) is of statistical significance. Evaluated significant relationship is indicated in bold. The correlation coefficients are also provided in Figs. 2 and 3 and Figs. S7 to S12 in Supplement S4.

Scenarios	All observations		(HAC) ² in FT (above PBL)		(HAC) ² in PBL		(HAC) ² in PBL without dust events		(HAC) ² in PBL with dust events		(HAC) ² ~ PBL top	
	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)
APS _{>0.5μm, total} ^a	0.69	0.52	0.40	0.45	0.35	0.39	0.46	0.53	0.73	0.65	0.65	0.54
	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
SMPS+APS _{total} ^a	0.45	0.29	0.13	0.03	0.51	0.46	0.05	0.11	0.15	0.23	0.33	0.25
	<0.01	0.01	0.27	0.81	<0.01	<0.01	0.70	0.37	0.20	0.06	0.05	0.04
SMPS _{<500nm} ^b	0.40	0.23	0.12	0.01	0.51	0.47	0.04	0.10	0.12	0.18	0.27	0.20
	<0.01	0.05	0.31	0.90	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.40	0.33	0.13	0.02	0.09
APS _{>0.5μm, <1.0μm} ^c	0.59	0.43	0.33	0.43	0.58	0.55	0.47	0.53	0.44	0.40	0.62	0.53
	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
APS _{>1.0μm, <1.5μm} ^d	0.71	0.62	0.43	0.42	0.09	0.08	0.37	0.34	0.77	0.77	0.63	0.55
	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.47	0.48	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
APS _{>1.5μm, <2.0μm} ^e	0.60	0.53	0.44	0.38	0.08	0.09	0.28	0.32	0.76	0.77	0.57	0.54
	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.49	0.46	0.02	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
APS _{>2.0μm, <2.5μm} ^f	0.58	0.53	0.43	0.35	0.10	0.09	0.24	0.31	0.75	0.75	0.51	0.46
	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.41	0.44	0.05	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
APS _{>2.5μm} ^g	0.64	0.54	0.46	0.40	0.15	0.14	0.30	0.34	0.70	0.65	0.57	0.49
	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.19	0.23	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

^aTotal particle (0.5 – 20 μ m) number concentration measured by APS; ^bTotal particle (0.01 – 20 μ m) number concentration measured by both SMPS and APS; ^cThe number concentration of particles smaller than 500 nm measured by SMPS; ^dThe number concentration of particles between 0.5 and 1.0 μ m measured by APS; ^eThe number concentration of particles between 1.0 and 1.5 μ m measured by APS; ^fThe number concentration of particles between 1.5 and 2.0 μ m measured by APS; ^gThe number concentration of particles between 2.0 and 2.5 μ m measured by APS; ^hThe number concentration of particles larger than 2.5 μ m measured by APS.

The dependence of INP diurnal cycles on aerosol particle size

To study the correlations between the diurnal variabilities of INPs and aerosol particle sizes, we compare the INP diurnal cycles with diurnal changes of the number concentration of total aerosol particles in different size ranges measured by a SMPS (10–800 nm, electrical mobility diameter) and an Aerodynamic Particle Sizer (0.5–20 μ m, aerodynamic diameter). Particles in different size ranges used to compare with INPs include SMPS+APS_{total} (0.01–20 μ m, Fig. S7), APS_{>0.5 μ m, total} (0.5–20 μ m, Fig. 2), SMPS_{<500nm} (Fig. S8), APS_{>0.5 μ m, <1.0 μ m} (Fig. S9), APS_{>1.0 μ m, <1.5 μ m} (Fig. S10), APS_{>1.5 μ m, <2.0 μ m} (Fig. S11), APS_{>2.0 μ m, <2.5 μ m} (Fig. S12) and APS_{>2.5 μ m} (Fig. 3). The definition of particles in each size range is provided in the footnote of Table 1. SMPS+APS_{total} is superimposed by both SMPS and APS results^{32,37}. Additionally, scatter plots comparing INP number concentrations with meteorological parameters (ambient T , horizontal wind velocity and direction) and different aerosol properties (fluorescent and optical properties, as well as eBC mass concentration) under different PBL conditions are provided

in Fig. S13 in Supplementary S5. Also, the correlation between INP diurnal cycles and eBC mass concentration and aerosol optical properties are also examined respectively (Figs. S14 to S16 in Supplementary S6).

195 Given the size dependence of INPs^{6,38}, $APS_{>0.5\mu\text{m}}$, total particles are assumed to be major INP contributors in the literature whereas smaller-sized particles ($<0.5\ \mu\text{m}$) are assumed to be insignificant INPs, which are even not included in some INP parameterizations^{7,39-40}. Coarse mode particles (e.g. $APS_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$) are relevant for dust and bioaerosols and considered with a higher probability of serving as INPs⁶⁻⁷. Here, we evaluate the contribution of $APS_{>0.5\mu\text{m}}$, total and $APS_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$ particles to the observed INPs under different atmospheric conditions (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3) and also discuss the importance of particles in other
200 size ranges (Table 1). The $APS_{>0.5\mu\text{m}}$, total (Fig. 2a) and $APS_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$ (Fig. 3a) concentration cycles from all observations show an overall diurnal cycle similar to that of INPs, respectively. Overall diurnal cycles and significant correlations with INPs are also observed for particles in other size ranges presented in Table 1 and Figs. S7a to S12a.

Analogous to the INP data for days only in FT, none of size-resolved particles presents a diurnal cycle (e.g. Fig. 2b and Fig. 3b), but all shows the lowest median value at the same hours as compared to the other scenarios influenced by PBL
205 air masses. Notably, Fig. 2b shows an overall constant $APS_{>0.5\mu\text{m}}$, total to INP concentration ratio (for median values) of approximately 250, while Fig. 3b presents that the difference between $APS_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$ and INP medians is generally within a factor of 10. Table 1 shows that particles having a size range larger than $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ have significant ($p<0.05$) and positive correlations with INPs throughout the day in FT whereas particles smaller than $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ ($SMPS_{<500\text{nm}}$) show an insignificant role, which highlights the importance of particles larger than $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ and is consistent with the literature^{7,39-40}. The case of $SMPS+APS_{\text{total}}$
210 in FT (Table 1 and Fig. S7b) presents similar results to that of $SMPS_{<500\text{nm}}$, given that $SMPS_{<500\text{nm}}$ takes a major fraction of $SMPS+APS_{\text{total}}$ ³².

For days when $(HAC)^2$ is only in the PBL, Table 1 shows that both $APS_{>0.5\mu\text{m}}$, total and $SMPS+APS_{\text{total}}$ present significant contributions to the observed INP diurnal cycles (also Fig. 2c and Fig. S7c). It also shows that only particles within a size range smaller than $1.0\ \mu\text{m}$ significantly contribute to INP diurnal cycles whereas particles with a larger size range (>1.0
215 μm) are weakly linked to INP variabilities. This may be because fine mode particles have much higher number concentrations than coarse mode particles³² and also because particles from various sources that span different size ranges are responsible for the observed INPs in the PBL³². Thus, a higher particle number concentration (despite being associated with smaller-sized particles) is associated with INP variability when aerosol sources affecting the aerosol population are many. Only when INP sources are further determined, can the importance of larger-sized particles for INP variability be determined, which is
220 demonstrated by the results in Table 1 for the case of $(HAC)^2$ in PBL with and without dust events. It shows that only particles in a size range larger than $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ have significant correlations to INP diurnal medians while smaller-sized particles ($SMPS_{<500\text{nm}}$ and $SMPS+APS_{\text{total}}$) are insignificant. This is consistent with the case of $(HAC)^2$ in FT and the literature^{7,39-40}. In addition, there are different size dependences for INP variability observed between cases of $(HAC)^2$ in PBL with and without dust events. Table 1 shows that with an increasing size range for particles larger than $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ (from a range of $0.5-1.0\ \mu\text{m}$ to a
225 range of larger than $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$), the significance of larger-sized particle become less and less pronounced for non-dust days. Again, this highlights a more important role of number concentration for particles to contribution to INPs in the PBL with

continental aerosols³², given that continental aerosols generally contain fine particles without dust events. Differently, the case of (HAC)² in PBL with dust events shows the least significant contributions of particles between 0.5 and 1.0 μm , compared to particles in larger size ranges ($>1.0 \mu\text{m}$), presenting the importance of larger-sized dust particles in regulating INP variabilities. 230 Notably, particles in size ranges larger than 1.0 μm show similar correlation and significance levels to INP variabilities (Table 1). This indicates dust particles enrich the observed INPs from a size limit of 1.0 μm , which is in agreement with Gao et al.³² (a parallel study) who reported a size distribution inflection point at 1.0 μm for aerosols observed at (HAC)² in PBL with the influence of dust events.

For the case of (HAC)²-PBL, it shows similar results to the case of all observations for the correlations between INPs 235 and particles in different size ranges (Table 1). Particles from all different size ranges play a significant role in regulating the INP diurnal cycle. It also presents a more important role for particles in a range larger than 0.5 μm compared with smaller particles. In brief, we conclude that particles larger than 0.5 μm are generally important contributors to the INP diurnal periodicity for (HAC)² in FT or PBL with and without dust events. When a mixture of varying INP sources is relevant, the contribution from smaller-sized particles ($<0.5 \mu\text{m}$) is non-negligible. Also, the different size dependence of INPs observed 240 for (HAC)² in PBL with and without dust events implies a different abundance of INP types in different sources.

The influence of biomass burning particles on INP diurnal variability

APS_{>0.5 μm , total} observed on days when (HAC)² is only in PBL without dust influence (Fig. 2d) shows an increase in the evening (~20:00–22:00), however, such an aerosol particle increase does not lead to increased INPs. Note that such a particle concentration spark is only present for particles in a range smaller than 1.5 μm (Figs. S8d to S10d). The presence of those 245 increased particles coincides with the peak values of elemental black carbon (eBC) mass concentration (measured by an aethalometer, AE31, Magee Scientific, US) in the evening (Fig. S13d in Supplementary S5), probably due to increased use of fossil fuels for heating during the cold days at the nearby village of Kalavryta (Supplementary Fig. S4d for low T_{ambient}). This is also supported by a positive and significant correlation between eBC mass concentration and the number concentration of total (observed by both SMPS and APS) particles smaller than 1.5 μm ($R=0.44$ ($p=8.31\text{E}-6$) and $\rho=0.68$ ($p=4.63\text{E}-14$)) for 250 (HAC)² in PBL without dust events but a negative and insignificant correlation with larger-sized ($>1.5 \mu\text{m}$) particles ($R=-0.11$ ($p=0.28$) and $\rho=-0.09$ ($p=0.39$)). Particles containing eBC masses or black carbon particles are poor INPs in the MPC regime⁴¹. Thus, those particles ($<1.5 \mu\text{m}$) containing eBC do not lead to INP increases. The above results in the evenings of non-dust days are similar to the results reported by Brunner et al.²³ for Jungfraujoch. Therefore, contributions from eBC-containing particles are negligible to INPs tested at $T=-25.2\pm 1.4^\circ\text{C}$ in this study.

260 **Fig. 4** Diurnal cycles of INP (tested at $T=-25.2\pm 1.4^{\circ}\text{C}$, on the left axis) and $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>0.5\mu\text{m, total}}$ (the number concentration of particles between 0.5 and $30\ \mu\text{m}$ showing fluorescence in any of three channels of a wideband integrated bioaerosol sensor (WIBS), on the right axis) measured at $(\text{HAC})^2$ under different atmospheric conditions. Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th quartiles. Different $(\text{HAC})^2$ atmospheric conditions are classified in different panels. (a) All observations during the campaign. (b) For days only in the FT. (c) For days only in the PBL. (d) Days in the PBL without dust events. (e) Days in the PBL with dust events. (f) Observations for days not exclusively in the PBL or FT. The data points of scenario are resampled for every 20 min and each panel shows a cycle period of 24 h starting at 00:00 UTC+2 (local time) of the day. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ), as well as corresponding p values, are provided to evaluate the correlation between INP concentration and $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>0.5\mu\text{m, total}}$. The p value is the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value if there is no liner correlation between INPs and $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>0.5\mu\text{m, total}}$. The number of data points (n) for each case of above statistical analysis is 72.

270 **Table 2.** The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ) for the relationship evaluation between diurnal INP median number concentration and the median number concentration of fluorescent biological aerosol particles (FBAPs) with different sizes under different atmospheric conditions. A critical p value of 0.05 from F-test for R (ρ) is used to assess the significance level of the relationship. A p value smaller than 0.05 suggests that the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value is less than 5% if there is actually no liner correlation between INPs and the given parameter, thus the calculated R (ρ) is of statistical significance. Evaluated significant relationship is indicated in bold. The correlation coefficients are also provided in Fig. 4 in the main text and Figs. S17 to S21 in Supplement S7.

Scenarios	All observations		(HAC) ² in FT (above PBL)		(HAC) ² in PBL		(HAC) ² in PBL without dust events		(HAC) ² in PBL with dust events		(HAC) ² ~ PBL top	
	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)	R (p)	ρ (p)
Flu _{OWIBS>0.5μm, total} ^a	0.67 <0.01	0.55 <0.01	0.21 0.08	0.18 0.13	0.62 <0.01	0.50 <0.01	0.72 <0.01	0.73 <0.01	0.26 0.03	0.20 0.09	0.65 <0.01	0.53 <0.01
Flu _{OWIBS>0.5μm, <1.0μm} ^b	0.43 <0.01	0.39 <0.01	-0.06 0.62	-0.05 0.68	0.59 <0.01	0.46 <0.01	0.70 <0.01	0.71 <0.01	0.17 0.17	0.21 0.07	0.34 <0.01	0.26 0.03
Flu _{OWIBS>1.0μm, <1.5μm} ^c	0.42 <0.01	0.42 <0.01	-0.06 0.62	-0.05 0.68	0.62 <0.01	0.56 <0.01	0.58 <0.01	0.62 <0.01	0.43 <0.01	0.53 <0.01	0.38 <0.01	0.41 <0.01
Flu _{OWIBS>1.5μm, <2.0μm} ^d	0.64 <0.01	0.60 <0.01	0.07 0.56	0.01 0.95	0.68 <0.01	0.61 <0.01	0.67 <0.01	0.67 <0.01	0.39 <0.01	0.49 <0.01	0.42 <0.01	0.46 <0.01
Flu _{OWIBS>2.0μm, <2.5μm} ^e	0.41 <0.01	0.43 <0.01	0.02 0.88	-0.03 0.78	0.70 <0.01	0.59 <0.01	0.75 <0.01	0.69 <0.01	0.39 <0.01	0.41 <0.01	0.29 0.01	0.30 0.01
Flu _{OWIBS>2.5μm} ^f	0.65 <0.01	0.58 <0.01	0.20 0.09	0.18 0.13	0.42 <0.01	0.38 <0.01	0.74 <0.01	0.70 <0.01	0.21 0.07	0.17 0.16	0.61 <0.01	0.56 <0.01

275 ^a Total particle (0.5 – 30 μ m) number concentration measured by WIBS; ^b The number concentration of particles between 0.5 and 1.0 μ m measured by WIBS; ^c The number concentration of particles between 1.0 and 1.5 μ m measured by WIBS; ^d The number concentration of particles between 1.5 and 2.0 μ m measured by WIBS; ^e The number concentration of particles between 2.0 and 2.5 μ m measured by WIBS; ^f The number concentration of particles larger than 2.5 μ m measured by WIBS.

The dependence of INP diurnal cycles on fluorescent biological aerosol particles in different size ranges

280 Particles of biological origin (even if not all INP-active) are effective INPs and key contributors to them in the MPC regime particularly for $T > -15^{\circ}\text{C}$ ⁴²⁻⁴³. Also, dust particles, important contributors to INPs for $T < -15^{\circ}\text{C}$ ⁴²⁻⁴³, are often found to be associated with materials of biological origin⁴⁴, like airborne bacteria coexisting with Saharan dust particles⁴⁵ and soil dust carrying biological materials upon dispersion⁴⁶. Fluorescence is an important property for particles carrying biological materials, despite some particles of non-biological origin can also fluoresce^{21,47}. Nevertheless, fluorescent particles have been frequently viewed as a lower-limit proxy for biological particles⁴⁸, called fluorescent biological aerosol particles (FBAPs)⁴⁷. Here, a Wideband Integrated Bioaerosol Sensor (WIBS, WIBS-5/NEO, Droplet Measurement Technologies, LLC. US) was used to measure the number concentration of fluorescent particles at (HAC)² and record the optical size of the particle (0.5–30 μ m)^{32,47}. Particles showing fluorescence in any one of the three WIBS fluorescent channels is attributed to Flu_{OWIBS} particles³² which includes all FBAPs detectable by a WIBS. FBAPs are demonstrated to be significant INP predictors in this CALISHTO campaign³² and also in field observations in other regions^{24,39}. Hence, we compare the diurnal cycles of both INPs and total FBAPs, represented by Flu_{OWIBS>0.5 μ m, total}, to investigate the role of bioaerosols in INP variabilities (Fig. 4). Also, we investigate the contribution of FBAPs in different size ranges to the observed INP diurnal cycles, including Flu_{OWIBS>0.5 μ m, <1.0 μ m} (Fig. S17), Flu_{OWIBS>1.0 μ m, <1.5 μ m} (Fig. S18), Flu_{OWIBS>1.5 μ m, <2.0 μ m} (Fig. S19), Flu_{OWIBS>2.0 μ m, <2.5 μ m} (Fig. S20) and Flu_{OWIBS>2.5 μ m} (Fig. S21). The calculated correlation coefficients are summarized in Table 2.

295 Table 2 shows an overall medium and significant correlations between the diurnal cycles of INP and FABP in all calculated size ranges (the column of all observations), suggesting FBAPs in different size ranges are generally important INP contributors. Of all size ranges, Flu_{OWIBS>1.5 μ m, <2.0 μ m} and Flu_{OWIBS>2.5 μ m} more important INP contributors, showing stronger

300 correlations with INPs than other size ranges. $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>1.5\mu\text{m}, <2.0\mu\text{m}}$ may coincide with the size range of large-sized bacteria or small-sized fungal spores generally smaller than $2.0\ \mu\text{m}$ and $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>2.5\mu\text{m}}$ may be of higher probability of fungal spores or larger-sized pollen fragments⁴⁹⁻⁵⁰, all of which are often found to be effective INPs⁵¹⁻⁵³. For $(\text{HAC})^2$ in FT, FBAPs in all size ranges show weak (both R and $\rho < 0.2$) and insignificant correlations with the observed INPs (Table 2). This suggests scarce FABPs in FT have very limited role in regulating INP variabilities, which, however, is regulated by aerosol particles larger than $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ (particularly $>2.5\ \mu\text{m}$) of different types (as shown in Table 1).

305 For $(\text{HAC})^2$ in PBL, FBAPs in all calculated size ranges show medium or stronger (e.g. $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>2.0\mu\text{m}, <2.5\mu\text{m}}$) correlations with INPs diurnal median values (Table 2). Compared with the combined case, FBAPs in each size range generally show much stronger (R and $\rho \geq 0.6$) correlations with INPs on non-dust days, while it shows less pronounced correlations (R and $\rho < 0.5$) with the presence of dust. This indicates a more important role of FABPs in contributing INPs when only continental and local aerosols are relevant INP sources at $(\text{HAC})^2$. Also, it suggests a non-negligible role of FBAPs as INP contributors during Saharan dust events. Altogether, this suggests that FBAPs relevant for INPs generally originate from PBL
310 aerosols in the absence of dust; during dust events, only FBAPs between 1.0 and $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$ are moderately and significantly correlated with the observed INPs, likely because smaller-sized FBAPs have a longer residence time and are easier to be mixed and transported with dust aerosols. However, much smaller-sized $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>0.5\mu\text{m}, <1.0\ \mu\text{m}}$ particles show weak and insignificant correlations with INPs during dust days (Table 2 and Fig. S17e) but a strong correlation during non-dust days. Likely, those particles of small sizes relevant for INPs can be ice-nucleating bacteria (later discussed with results presented in Table 3 and
315 Supplementary S8) – as local and continental aerosols may contain more bacteria whereas transported Saharan dust across less polluted Mediterranean may carry less. Additionally, we note that eBC-containing particles as interfering FBAPs⁴⁷ may be responsible for the small peak of $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}>0.5\mu\text{m}, \text{total}}$ at 20:00-22:00 hrs in Fig. 4d, which is only pronounced for FBAPs smaller than $1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ (Figs. S17d and 18d). Again, the results in the case of $(\text{HAC})^2$ -PBL (i.e. $(\text{HAC})^2$ fluctuates around PB/FT interface) are similar to the case of all observations, possibly because both cases contain a mixture of varying types of FABPs.
320 In summary, Table 2 shows that both FBAPs and dust particles are important sources of INPs, but INP variabilities on non-dust days are more dependent on FBAPs whereas FBAPs are a less important (but still non-negligible) contributor during dust events because of contributions from dust particles.

325 **Fig. 5. Diurnal cycles of INP (tested at $T=-25.2\pm 1.4^\circ\text{C}$, on the left axis) and ABC_{WIBS} (the number concentration of particles between**
0.5 and $30\ \mu\text{m}$ showing fluorescence in all three WIBS channels, on the right axis) measured at $(\text{HAC})^2$ under different atmospheric
conditions. Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th
quartiles. Different $(\text{HAC})^2$ atmospheric conditions are classified in different panels. (a) All observations during the campaign. (b)
For days only in the FT. (c) For days only in the PBL. (d) Days in the PBL without dust events. (e) Days in the PBL with dust events.
330 **(f) Observations for days not exclusively in the PBL or FT. The data points of scenario are resampled for every 20 min and each**
panel shows a cycle period of 24 h starting at 00:00 UTC+2 (local time) of the day. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and
Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ), as well as corresponding p values, are provided to evaluate the correlation between INP
concentration and ABC_{WIBS} . The p value is the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value if there
is no liner correlation between INPs and ABC_{WIBS} . The number of data points (n) for each case of above statistical analysis is 72.

335 **Table 3. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and Spearman's rank coefficient (ρ) for the relationship evaluation between diurnal**
INP median number concentration and the median number concentration of different types of fluorescent biological aerosol particles
(FBAPs) under different atmospheric conditions. A critical p value of 0.05 from F-test for R (ρ) is used to assess the significance level
of the relationship. A p value smaller than 0.05 suggests that the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R
(ρ) value is less than 5% if there is actually no liner correlation between INPs and the given parameter, thus the calculated R (ρ) is
340 **of statistical significance. Evaluated significant relationship is indicated in bold. The correlation coefficients are also provided in Fig.**
5 in the main text and Figs. S22 to S27 in Supplement S8.

Scenarios	All observations		$(\text{HAC})^2$ in FT (above PBL)		$(\text{HAC})^2$ in PBL		$(\text{HAC})^2$ in PBL without dust events		$(\text{HAC})^2$ in PBL with dust events		$(\text{HAC})^2 \sim$ PBL top	
	R	ρ	R	ρ	R	ρ	R	ρ	R	ρ	R	ρ
	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)	(p)

A_{WIBS}^a	0.65 <0.01	0.67 <0.01	0.22 0.08	0.24 0.05	0.68 <0.01	0.61 <0.01	0.81 <0.01	0.77 <0.01	0.40 <0.01	0.43 <0.01	0.44 <0.01	0.50 <0.01
B_{WIBS}^b	0.51 <0.01	0.39 <0.01	-0.10 0.40	-0.05 0.67	0.64 <0.01	0.47 <0.01	0.63 <0.01	0.66 <0.01	0.29 0.01	0.33 0.01	0.36 <0.01	0.25 0.04
C_{WIBS}^c	0.53 <0.01	0.54 <0.01	0.15 0.20	0.08 0.52	0.53 <0.01	0.49 <0.01	0.70 <0.01	0.69 <0.01	0.32 <0.01	0.28 0.02	0.28 0.02	0.28 0.02
AB_{WIBS}^d	0.45 <0.01	0.70 <0.01	-0.09 0.53	-0.18 0.19	0.59 <0.01	0.44 <0.01	0.65 <0.01	0.68 <0.01	0.32 0.01	0.36 <0.01	0.41 <0.01	0.65 <0.01
AC_{WIBS}^e	0.38 <0.01	0.51 <0.01	-0.07 0.72	0.12 0.57	0.33 0.01	0.47 <0.01	0.51 <0.01	0.71 <0.01	0.28 0.02	0.22 0.06	0.12 0.32	0.22 0.06
BC_{WIBS}^f	0.58 <0.01	0.51 <0.01	0.10 0.40	0.05 0.71	0.55 <0.01	0.42 <0.01	0.70 <0.01	0.72 <0.01	0.16 0.18	0.15 0.22	0.49 <0.01	0.44 <0.01
ABC_{WIBS}^g	0.52 <0.01	0.51 <0.01	0.08 0.48	0.09 0.47	0.67 <0.01	0.55 <0.01	0.78 <0.01	0.72 <0.01	0.40 <0.01	0.40 <0.01	0.44 <0.01	0.52 <0.01

^a The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in WIBS FL1 channel; ^b The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in WIBS FL2 channel; ^c The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in WIBS FL3 channel; ^d The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in both WIBS FL1 and FL2 channels; ^e The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in both WIBS FL1 and FL3 channels; ^f The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in both WIBS FL2 and FL3 channels, ^g The total number concentration of particles showing fluorescence only in all WIBS FL1, FL2 and FL3 channels.

The dependence of INP diurnal cycles on different types of fluorescent biological aerosol particles

Different types of biological particles may exhibit different fluorescence characteristics in the WIBS⁴⁷, and when considered in our analysis (together with size ranges expected for each population) can help further understand the specific contribution of each biological type to observed INP. A detailed FABP types classification is provided in Table 3. In general, bacteria show fluorescence dominantly in WIBS FL1 channel and can be recorded as A_{WIBS} (dominant), AB_{WIBS} and ABC_{WIBS} particles around 1.0 μm but less than 2.0 μm ⁴⁹⁻⁵⁰. Fungal spores and fungi are also frequently detected as A_{WIBS} (dominant), AB_{WIBS} and ABC_{WIBS} particles, but are larger than 2.0 μm ^{47,50}. Intact and fragmented pollen grains are often recognized as C_{WIBS} , BC_{WIBS} and ABC_{WIBS} (dominant) particles larger than 2.0 μm ^{47,50}. ABC_{WIBS} type particles are reported as fluorescent particles measured by a WIBS of the highest probability of being biological particles^{47,50} and with less influence from interfering non-biological particles like black carbon and dust particles associated with fluorescent materials^{21,47}.

Table 3 shows that all types of FBAPs are moderately or even strongly correlated with INPs in the overall diurnal cycle, likely suggesting the relevance of varying types of biological particles to the observed INPs during the whole campaign. Similar results but with less stronger correlations were observed for the case of (HAC)²~PBL. For days when (HAC)² was exclusively in the FT, the diurnal cycle of INPs is insignificantly correlated with any types of FBAPs. However, the median number concentration values of INPs are generally within a factor of 3 compared to those of A_{WIBS} , B_{WIBS} , C_{WIBS} , BC_{WIBS} and ABC_{WIBS} particles (e.g. Fig. 5b). Those suggest that biological particles in FT airmasses are non-negligible INP sources. For days when (HAC)² resides exclusively in the PBL (e.g. Fig. 5c), the diurnal cycle of all different types of FBAPs is significantly correlated with the corresponding INP cycle (e.g. ABC_{WIBS} R=0.67 and $p<0.01$), which become much stronger on non-dust

370 days (e.g. ABC_{WIBS} with $R=0.78$ in Fig. 5d) but weaker on dust days (e.g. ABC_{WIBS} with $R=0.40$ in Fig. 5e). The generally much stronger correlations between the diurnal cycles of INPs and all different types of FBAPs for non-dust days in PBL compared with those of dust days suggest the overall enrichment of different types of biological particles for non-dust days. Also, it indicates that continental and local aerosols are the primary sources of biological particles but not the transported dust plume, which is consistent with the aerosol source apportionment conducted in a parallel study³² and also results in Table 2. The above demonstrate FBAPs are primary drivers of the INP diurnal cycles observed at $(HAC)^2$ in PBL.

375 **Fig. 6. Diurnal cycles of different types of fluorescent biological aerosol particles on days without (left axis) and with (right axis) dust events. Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th quartiles. (a) $Fluor_{WIBS}$, (b) ABC_{WIBS} , (c) A_{WIBS} , (d) B_{WIBS} , (e) C_{WIBS} , (f) AB_{WIBS} , (g) AC_{WIBS} and (h) BC_{WIBS} .**

The influence of dust events on aerosol property and INP diurnal variability

Remotely-transported dust plumes modulate aerosols and INPs at (HAC)² in the PBL. We present the influences of dust events on aerosol property observed at (HAC)² by comparing the diurnal cycles of size-resolved total aerosol particle (Fig. S28) and FBAP number concentration (Fig. S29), as well as different types of FBAP (Fig. 6), observed on non-dust days with dust days.

380 Further discussions on the correlations between aerosol property changes and INP variabilities (see Fig. 2 to 5) for both cases will be conducted. The results in Fig. S28 show that total aerosol particles with size smaller than 0.5 μm during non-dust days are more than those on dust days by at least a factor of 10 (panel c). Dust events enrich particles in size ranges larger than 1.0 μm (panel e to h) for dust days by a factor of 5~10 compared with those of non-dust days. Similarly, comparing with dust days, Fig. S29 shows that non-dust days contain more FBAPs of size below 2.0 μm (panel b, c and d) but less FBAPs larger than

385 2.5 μm (panel f). These results suggest continental aerosols enriched with fine mode aerosols dominate the INPs during non-dust days and exhibit substantially different size and contribution of INPs in comparison with dust episode days, and is consistent with Gao et al.³² for air mass characteristics at (HAC)².

Fig. 6 generally show that dust days have much higher number concentration of total FBAPs indicated by Fluow_{WIBS} in the morning from 00:00 to 08:00 hrs. The enriched FABPs are primarily attributed to C_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS} particles (Fig. 6e and h) often reported to be associated with dust events and biological particles⁴⁷. The enriched C_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS} may be large-sized (3–10 μm as seen in Fig. 6e from Gao et al.³²) dust-containing particles that are more effective INP (Fig. S29f) than seen for smaller particles, thus can explain the higher INP concentrations on dust days (Fig. 2e to 5e) compared with those on non-dust days (Fig. 2d to 5d).

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From 08:00 to 16:00 hrs, Fluow_{WIBS} particles on non-dust days majorly consist of ABC_{WIBS}, B_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS} particles, while Fluow_{WIBS} particles on dust days mostly include ABC_{WIBS}, A_{WIBS}, C_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS} particles (Fig. 6). The higher concentration of ABC_{WIBS} (by a factor of ~2) and B_{WIBS} particles (by a factor of ~4) on non-dust days may explain their high number concentration of INP (by ~50%) compared with those on dust-days, given that ABC_{WIBS} are of highest probability of being biological particles^{32,47} thus IN-active at warm temperatures. B_{WIBS} particles on non-dust days are likely from continental aerosols smaller than 2.0 μm (see Fig. 6c in Gao et al.³²), and may be related to bacteria that may be IN active⁵³. Differently,

400 the enriched A_{WIBS} and C_{WIBS} particles on dust days are probably of sizes between 3 and 10 μm (see Fig. 6a and d in Gao et al.³²), which can be attributed to fungal spores and/or fragmented pollen grains of similar sizes^{47,50} or small bacteria combined with large-sized dust particles⁴⁵. Additionally, the higher concentrations of FABPs for both non-dust and dust days between 08:00 and 16:00 hrs than the other periods of the day coincide with the noon peaks of INPs for both cases (Fig. 2 to 5). Notably, the peak of INPs on non-dust days at 12:00 hrs overall shows an overlap with that of ABC_{WIBS} (Fig. 5d and Fig. 6b) but not

405 for APS_{>2.5 μm} particles (Fig. 3d), supporting that the contribution of FBAPs to the observed INPs is more important than the total coarse-sized aerosol particles. In contrast, the coincided overlaps of INP and BC_{WIBS} (APS_{>2.5 μm}) particles on dust days as shown in Fig. 6h (Fig. 3e) may confirm the significant role of dust particles as INP contributors.

From 16:00 hrs to the end of the day, Fluow_{WIBS} particles on non-dust days are up to twofold higher than for dust days (Fig. 6a). Those enriched FABPs on non-dust days are generally contributed by ABC_{WIBS}, B_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS} particles (panel 410 b, d and h). In particular, the elevated concentration levels of FABPs (ABC_{WIBS}, B_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS}) coincide with the spark of INP evening peak (by 50%, from 20:00 to 22:00 in Fig. 2d to 5d) on non-dust days, suggesting the contribution of FBAPs to the increase in INPs. In contrast, a relatively constant FABP median concentration (e.g. Fluow_{WIBS} and the other types) corresponds to a stable INP abundance during the same period (Fig. 2e to 5e). Therefore, FBAP and dust particles are the key drivers for the INP diurnal cycles observed at (HAC)². ABC_{WIBS} and B_{WIBS} FBAPs are the most important particles regulating 415 INPs in the PBL without dust events. Dust events can substantially enrich larger-sized dust containing FABPs (A_{WIBS} and C_{WIBS}) during noon time when PBL is high (suggesting that airmasses in PBL may also be of the sources of A_{WIBS} and C_{WIBS} FBAPs), while they supply more C_{WIBS} and BC_{WIBS} FABPs when PBLH is below the (HAC)², which contribute to the INP when the site is outside of the PBL (nighttime).

Vertical INP distributions with respect to PBL/FT interface for each atmospheric classification

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Fig. 7 INP concentration distribution as a function PBLH. The color scale shows the ice nucleation experiment temperature. Solid lines indicate the median value and the shading area around the median line shows the range between 25th and 75th quartiles. INP data was filtered within a small temperature range as indicated in each panel, to reduce the temperature dependence of INPs. Different (HAC)² atmospheric conditions are classified in different panels. (a) All observations during the campaign. (b) For days only in the FT. (c) For days only in the PBL. (d) Days in the PBL without dust events. (e) Days in the PBL with dust events. (f) Observations for days not exclusively in the PBL or FT. Data points were resampled for every 20 min. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) and the Spearman rank coefficient (ρ), as well as corresponding p values, are provided to evaluate the correlation between INP concentration and PBLH. The p value is the probability of obtaining an R (ρ) value no smaller than the true R (ρ) value if there is no linear correlation between INP concentration and PBLH. The n value is the number of data points for the statistical analysis.

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Fig. 7 illustrates INP concentration distributions with PBLH under different atmospheric conditions. In general, INPs show a positive and significant linear correlation with increasing PBLH (Fig. 7a). For days exclusively in the FT (Fig. 7b), INPs

overall decrease with decreasing PBLH, showing a statistically significant ($p=5.37\times 10^{-3}$) but weak correlation level ($R=0.25$). This means that INPs become rarer deeper inside the FT, as the total aerosol particles do (Supplementary Figs. S31b to S36b).

435 For days only in PBL without dust events (Fig. 7d), INPs show small variations with changing PBLH. This is because airmasses in the PBL are intensively mixed⁵⁴ and most aerosol particles in the PBL generally show insignificant dependence on the PBLH (Figs. S31d to S33d), except FBAPs, i.e., FluowIBS and ABCwIBS (Figs. S34d and S35d). Supplementary Figs. S34d and S35d present that both FluowIBS and ABCwIBS for non-dust days increase with increasing PBLH, showing strong correlations ($R=0.72$ and 0.64 respectively). The reason for the different dependence of INPs and FBAPs on the PBLH for the case of days

440 in the PBL without dust may be twofold. First, considering the active ice nucleation ability of bioaerosols that activate as ice at warm temperatures ($>-20^{\circ}\text{C}$)³⁹, FBAPs may only partly contribute to INPs tested at colder temperatures ($\sim-27^{\circ}\text{C}$) in PBL case. In addition, FBAPs, such as ABCwIBS and FluowIBS, may not include the total number of particles with biological material that contribute to the observed INPs. For days when (HAC)² was only in PBL with dust events (Fig. 7e), the INP concentration does not vary significantly with changing PBLH and it shows an INP peak close to PBLH=1.0 km. The peak can be explained

445 by the peak (also for PBLH=1.0 km) of $\text{APS}_{>2.5\mu\text{m}}$ as a function of PBLH (Supplementary Fig. S33e), given that coarse-sized particles are more effective INPs. For days not exclusively in the PBL or FT (Fig. 7f), the positive correlation between INP and PBLH is moderate and significant, similar to the overall observations for the campaign.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We demonstrate the existence of diurnal INPs cycles for moderately-cool mixed-phase orographic clouds ($\sim-25^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the E.

450 Mediterranean and determine their drivers. The diurnal cycles of aerosols sourced from planetary boundary layer (PBL; e.g., bioaerosol) and remotely transported particles (e.g., Saharan dust) regulate the INP periodicity and levels. A strong diurnal INP cycle is seen when the observation site resides in the PBL and practically vanishes when in the free troposphere (FT). In particular, we reveal the relative importance of different INP sources, including bioaerosols, dust and eBC-containing particles, on the observed INP diurnal cycles. We show that INPs in FT come from total aerosol particles in different size ranges larger

455 $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ (Table 1) but are not correlated with any types of fluorescent biological aerosol particles (FBAPs, Table 3). This highlights the INP population observed in the FT is different from that in the PBL. Likely, this is because INPs in the FT are far away transported and aged particles, where as INPs in the PBL are much closer to their sources, e.g. biological particles. This is also indicative of the necessities of further studies on the source apportionment of INPs in the FT, which is also suggested by Gao et al.³² and will be investigated in our next field campaign at (HAC)².

460 The diurnal cycle of FBAPs in the PBL significantly contribute to the INP cycles at warm MPC temperatures ($>-20^{\circ}\text{C}$). Abrupt INP source changes from dust plume intrusions, can perturb the diurnal variability and vertical distribution of INP. In the presence of Saharan dust drives INP variability by enriched larger-sized particles ($>1.0\ \mu\text{m}$; Table 1), while in its absence INPs are overall more linked to particles of size between 0.5 and $1.0\ \mu\text{m}$ (Table 1). The elevated concentration of coarse-sized dust particles during Saharan dust events does not significantly increase INPs during daytime because the uplifting of PBL

465 airmasses with increased PBLH may bring more continental aerosol that impedes the dust plume intrusions or mixes with
dusty aerosols inducing aging and INP activity suppression. The competition between uplifting PBL airmasses and dust plume
intrusions may also reduce the supply of bioaerosols from the lower PBL. During nighttime with Saharan dust events, coarse-
sized dust particles can increase INPs when the availability of PBL airmasses is low because of PBL contraction, which
diminishes the variance of INPs throughout the day. Thus, the different contribution of dust particles during daytime and
470 nighttime provides a control test and reveals the important role of bioaerosols for INPs in the MPC regime during daytime. It
is also notable that $\text{Fluo}_{\text{WIBS}}$ concentrations explain more than 90% of INP concentrations during the dust event. Additionally,
we demonstrate that eBC-containing particles (originating from anthropogenic activities or wildfires) play a negligible role in
the diurnal periodicity of INPs in the MPC regime.

In conclusion, we show that the diurnal cycles of INPs for orographic clouds in the E. Mediterranean is driven by the PBL
475 airmasses, and that bioaerosols are a major driver of this variability in the absence of dust. The presence of dust influences the
variabilities of both FBAPs and INPs, showing enrichment in INPs particularly in the morning when PBL aerosol sources is
less available with low PBLHs. Considering that bioaerosols are present at forested mountainous regions, they are one of the
key regulators that primarily modulates the ice formation in orographic clouds and may also influence secondary ice
production¹⁸. Such INP sources and diurnal forcing of clouds are rarely considered in models but are expected, based on the
480 generality and ubiquity of the sources determined here. Given this and the importance of bioaerosol and the correct vertical
distribution of INPs for the formation of extreme precipitation in mountainous environments¹⁸ and potentially for cloud system
development¹⁷, it becomes clear that such sources and corresponding cycles may be underappreciated drivers of cloud
formation, aerosol-cloud interactions and extreme events.

METHODS

485 CALISHTO field campaign

To investigate aerosol-cloud interactions (including INP abundance and variability) in the eastern Mediterranean region, a
field campaign, called the Cloud-Aerosol InteractionS in the Helmos background Troposphere (CALISHTO,
<https://calishto.panacea-ri.gr/>)^{18,31-33} was carried out on the basis of the Hellenic Atmospheric Aerosol and Climate Change
station (termed (HAC)², ~2.3 km a.s.l., 37.984033° N and 22.196060° E) at Mount Helmos (Greece) between October and
490 November 2021. (HAC)² is an observation site that allows the study of INPs both under the PBL and FT conditions⁵⁵ because
of its high altitude. The instrumentation set-up and timeseries results of different measurements are presented in Supplementary
Figs. S1 and S2, respectively. An online INP spectrometer called Portable Ice Nucleation Experiment (PINE)²⁸ was used to
measure INP concentrations at (HAC)² from an omnidirectional total inlet with a temporal resolution of 6~7 minutes. The
PINE inlet has a 80% sampling efficiency for particles between 3 and 5 μm , and it decreases to approximately 50% for particles
495 between 5 and 10 μm . In this study, the PINE was operated in a T range from ~ -24 to -27 °C and S_w (saturation ratio with
respect to water) >1.0 to measure INPs activating as ice in all freezing mode³². A wind Doppler Lidar (HALO, StreamLine

Wind Pro model, HALO Photonics), deployed at a lower site than (HAC)² (by ~0.5 km), was used to measure the PBLH and to determine the (HAC)² position with respect to the PBL. Aerosol properties and meteorological parameters at (HAC)² were monitored simultaneously to understand the variations of observed INPs. The characterized aerosol properties include the number concentration of aerosol particles larger than 95 nm recorded by a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS_{>95nm and <800nm}, SMPS model 3938, TSI Inc., US, measuring particle size distributions in the 10 to 800 nm diameter size range), the total concentration of aerosol particles (0.5–20 μm, aerodynamic diameter) recorder by an aerodynamic particle sizer (Total_{APS}, APS model 3321, TSI Inc., US), the concentration of particles (0.5–30 μm, optical diameter) showing fluorescence from three fluorescent channels of a wideband integrated bioaerosol sensor (WIBS-5/NEO, Droplet Measurement Technologies, LLC. US), the scattering coefficient at 450 nm (Scatt450nm) and Ångström exponent at the 450-700 nm wavelength pair measured by a nephelometer (Model 3563, TSI Inc., US), as well as the mass concentration of elemental black carbon (eBC) measured by an aethalometer (AE31, Magee Scientific, US). The recorded meteorological parameters include wind velocity and direction data, relative humidity *wrt.* water (RH_w) and ambient temperature (T_{ambient}). In addition, dust particle mass concentrations at different altitudes are calculated by the SKIRON model⁵⁶⁻⁵⁷ to diagnose the presence of Sahara dust events. The field campaign lasts for more than 6 weeks from October 12 to November 24, 2021.

Planetary boundary layer (PBL) condition determination

The HALO wind lidar measures the vertical velocity of air masses carrying micron-sized aerosol particles at a stare mode emitting pulsed laser beams at 1.5 μm. Using the Doppler effect, the radial wind velocity along the direction of the laser beam can be retrieved and the distance between scatters (aerosols) in the beam path can be calculated⁵⁸⁻⁵⁹. The maximum detection range varies from 2.0 to 3.0 km depending on the micron-sized aerosol load in the atmosphere⁶⁰. More detailed information about the measurements and calculation for PBLH can be found in our parallel work³¹⁻³² for the CALISHITO campaign. To determine the PBL condition at (HAC)² for time periods when PBLH is missing due to insufficient micron-sized aerosol load, a SMPS $N_{>95\text{nm}}$ threshold value of 100 std cm⁻³ was used to diagnose the position of (HAC)² relative to the PBL^{27,34}. For SMPS_{>95nm and <800nm} > 100 std cm⁻³, it means (HAC)² is within the PBL. Otherwise, it may be above PBL and more in the FT.

The determination of dust events

To determine the presence of dust events around (HAC)², the dust mass concentration calculated by the SKIRON model⁵⁶⁻⁵⁷ and the Ångström exponent³² at the 450-700 nm wavelength pair (see Supplementary S1) measured by nephelometer are used⁶¹. From Supplementary Fig. S2f, dust mass concentration decreases with decreasing altitude below (HAC)². Thus, the dust mass concentration at (HAC)² may be higher than the concentration calculated by the model at the highest altitude (2.17 km). Also, the Ångström exponent is compared to a threshold value of 1.0 and a smaller Ångström exponent value indicates the presence of dust events at (HAC)². Additionally, the footprints of air masses from Sahara are provided by air mass dynamic simulations in our parallel work to confirm the dust plumes originate from the Saharan desert.

Daily based data classification based on (HAC)² condition with respect to the PBL

530 An observation day will be classified as the scenario of (HAC)² only in the PBL (or (HAC)² only in the FT) if the PBLH is larger (or lower) than 0.5 km for more than 23 h throughout day, which otherwise will be attributed to a day neither exclusively in the FT nor in the PBL ((HAC)²~PBL top). When PBLH data is missing, SMPS_{>95nm and <800nm} results will be used to diagnose the atmospheric condition. Based on the above criteria and considering the influence of dust events, we classify the daily results into four cases as introduced in the main text, to calculate the diurnal cycles of INPs and aerosol properties using 20 min averaged data. The median values and 25th to 75th percentiles (Q_{25%}–Q_{75%}) are used to describe the INP and aerosol particle concentration levels in the diurnal cycles. This is because, away from sources, atmospheric aerosol particles tend to be log-normally distributed⁶². Assuming the log-normally distributed data without any skewness, the median value equals to the log-normal mean value. Therefore, we report the median results as Brunner et al²⁷.

DATA AVAILABILITY

540 The data presented in this publication will be made available at <https://www.envidat.ch>. The DOI link will be activated for public access upon acceptance of publication.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

555 AN, AP and KE lead and coordinated the CALISHTO campaign. KuG and AN conceived and led this study. KuG led the analysis, wrote the original manuscript together with AN. KuG prepared all the figures with contributions from RF, AMB and SV. RF setup and operated the radar and wind lidar instrumentation. FV and OM provided the PINE timeseries. All authors discussed the manuscript and provided feedback.

COMPETING INTERESTS

560 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Supplement information is provided to support the results and discussions in the main text.

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